

HOW THE PERCEPTION OF WOMEN IN STAR WARS CHANGES

by

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Abstract

In 1977, *Star Wars* hit the screens as an overwhelming success; yet despite its popularity, it has struggled with diversity and inclusivity from the time of its creation until today. I examined the development of women present throughout the *Star Wars* Skywalker Saga by looking at the nine episodes of *Star Wars*, *Star Wars* books, and *The Clone Wars* animated movie and series. The portrayal of females within the franchise has changed as time passes – in particular with an accelerated transformation when Disney purchased *Star Wars* in 2012. For example, in *Return of the Jedi*, Carrie Fisher's Princess Leia is forced to be Jabba the Hutts' slave and is dubbed "Slave Leia," but a book published in 2016 titled *Bloodline* renames her to Huttslayer, aligning with the women's rights movements and giving Leia back her power. By looking at the creation of the *Star Wars* universe, the impact of the franchise on fans, as well as Disney's purchase of the franchise in 2012, it is clear that what began as one movie marketed towards males slowly began to create more content and characters for an audience that included women. The Disney *Star Wars* sequels star the first Jedi female lead; however, the simple act of inclusion does not erase the fact that Rey's story is nearly identical to her male predecessor's, Luke Skywalker. With that said, there is a positive progression of how women in *Star Wars* are treated on and off the screen, but – as with anything – there is always room for improvement.

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Introduction

"It was one movie. It wasn't supposed to do what it did—nothing was supposed to do that. Nothing ever had. Movies were meant to stay on the screen, flat and large and colorful, gathering you up into their sweep of story, carrying you rollicking along to the end, then releasing you back into your unchanged life. But this movie misbehaved" (Fisher, *The Princess Diarist*, 2016, p. 194). The movie Carrie Fisher is referring to is, of course, *Star Wars*.

When the box-office record making movie came out in 1977, it was just *Star Wars*; the end title to the movie (*A New Hope*) had not yet been added (IMDb, n.d.). Since its release, there have been eight other episodes, an animated movie, an animated series, and books making up the Skywalker Saga as it was aptly named after the primary family involved in the galactic conflicts. This paper focuses primarily on the women within the Skywalker storyline as it was the first and longest. Other movies, books, shows, and comics do now exist that detail different conflicts in the galaxy far, far away. These cover new territory like *The High Republic* that happens years before the Skywalker storyline or new characters such as Cassian Andor who are not directly linked to the main characters of the Skywalker Saga.

An important distinction must be made in the timeline of the Star Wars franchise as Star Wars has two 'eras.' More specifically, there is the original trilogy and the prequel trilogy that combine to create the pre-Disney era led by creator George Lucas. Disney purchased Lucasfilm for \$4 billion in 2012 (Krantz, Snider, Cava, & Alexander, 2012), creating the post-Disney era which includes the three sequel episodes as well as a new timeline told through shows, books, and movies.

Star Wars began as one movie, marketed towards males as is evident by the early toy commercials which showed little boys as the focal point for all toys. Little girls were only in the advertisements if they portrayed the little sister. The franchise has since grown, and as it has, it has slowly begun to create content and characters for an audience that includes women. Throughout this transition, it will become clear that sometimes the progression of female characters is motivated by the potential earnings related to gender-based marketing or as a general response to current social movements. Other times, the development of female progress within the *Star Wars* franchise will be intrinsic and come from a focus of developing a good story through its characters. Throughout both eras, choices are made by Lucasfilm and fans that serve to develop or destroy female characters through their creation or their own actions and opinions. Through the course of the *Star Wars* franchise's history, the idea that women should be respectfully and equitably represented alongside their male counterparts grew and spread throughout the *Star Wars* universe to create a more inclusive and diverse fandom.

Women and Star Wars

This story begins with Carrie Fisher, just 19 years old, receiving the phone call that would change her life and pop culture forever. She was to become Princess Leia Organa, but there was a caveat: she had to lose 10 pounds. It is unlikely that Harrison Ford or Mark Hamill had such contingencies attached to their employment. Though later Mark Hamill would be required to lose weight for his role in *The Force Awakens* along with Fisher (O'Toole, 2015). It's all about appearance, and unfortunately for actresses, they have to be thin and attractive to attract the necessary attention. Despite going to a fat farm in Texas prior to the filming of the original *Star Wars*, she was unable to lose the

required weight. This fact made her agreeable to anything, so they would not notice she had not lost the required weight.

Life on set was anything but diverse; Fisher described the crew as being “mostly men. That’s how it was” (Fisher, *The Princess Diarist*, 2016, p. 33). One of the exceptions being Pat McDermott who was Fisher’s hairdresser. They would spend countless hours together deciding on the hairstyle that would eventually become synonymous with Princess Leia including “a variety of exotic looks—from Russian princess to Swedish maids” (Fisher, *The Princess Diarist*, 2016, p. 39). In order to capture Leia’s “not a damsel in distress” personality, they eventually settled on the iconic cinnamon buns. Fisher, not really a fan of this hairstyle exclaimed her love for it so as to not draw attention to her lack of weight loss. George Lucas claimed the hairstyle was modeled after a “south-western Pancho Villa woman revolutionary look” (Drury, 2016); however, this sweeping classification is not completely true.

In looking through photos of revolutionary women who fought with Pancho Villa, or *soldaderas*, there is one woman who sticks out as potentially being George Lucas’ inspiration to the Princess Leia cinnamon bun hairstyle; otherwise, it seems more likely that the inspiration behind this Pancho Villa woman’s hairstyle is the Hopi Native American tribe. (Rejected Princess, n.d.) The woman in Figure 1 shows Clara de la Rocha, a woman who fought in the Mexican Revolution (Durango, n.d.), while the young women in Figure 2 are from the Hopi Native American tribe.

Figure 1 A soldaderas named Clara de la Rocha who fought in the Mexican Revolution in 1911 (Distasio, 2021)

Figure 2 Hopi Girls Grinding Corn is a reproduction "of vintage photograph by John K. Hillers: b. 1843 d. 1925. American explorer, and recorder of" Native Americans. (Hillers & Prusso, 2012)

Perhaps the irony to this misunderstanding is the difference between the symbolic nature of a Pancho Villa woman and the Hopi Native American squash blossom hairstyle. Where a Pancho Villa independent woman is fighting in a revolution channeling Princess Leia's fiery spirit, the Hopi Native American tribe squash blossom whorl is not. In Hopi tradition, "unmarried Hopi girls wore their hair protruding from both sides of the head in the shape of a squash blossom, a style unique to the Hopi" (Hopi, 2017, pp. 337-342). The wearing of this hairstyle suggests that the woman is now ready for marriage as it is a

transition from childhood to adulthood issued on the onset of puberty. (MessyNessy, 2018) This contradiction is interesting – however unintentional as it may be – it serves as a subtle reminder that neither Leia nor Fisher were treated as equals to their male counterparts.

At George Lucas' birthday party during the filming of the first *Star Wars* film, Fisher was subjected to the negative reality of being one of the only women on set. During this particular party, Fisher was the only girl in attendance. Some crew members thought "it would be entertaining to have the only girl at the party completely off-her-ass drunk" (Fisher, *The Princess Diarist*, 2016, p. 66). Fisher, knowing that she and alcohol did not get along, resisted the crew's pressuring at first. However, Fisher being 19 years old and a people-pleaser, caved to the alcohol insistent crew members becoming senseless by the end of the night. At some point during the night Fisher "became aware that quite a few members of the crew were organizing a kind of joke abduction of" her (Fisher, *The Princess Diarist*, 2016, p. 70). One could say that Harrison Ford was her savior from whatever the cast had planned for that night, but at the same time, the events of that night eventually turned into the start of an affair between the married 33-year-old Harrison Ford and the 19-year-old Carrie Fisher.

The Power Struggle of Princess Leia and Carrie Fisher

On screen, Carrie Fisher's Princess Leia Organa denies being part of the Rebel Alliance when Darth Vader rightly accuses. She asserts to this imposing villain that she was on a diplomatic mission to Alderaan, her home planet. In reality, she is part of the Rebel Alliance and has just secured the secret plans for the Empire's deadly weapon, the

Death Star. Her courage to stand up to Darth Vader (who is later seen choking someone) is noted, and she is seen as an equal throughout the film to her male counterparts.

But on set, Fisher was forced to forgo undergarments. George Lucas, the creator of *Star Wars*, told her she couldn't wear a bra under her iconic white dress from *Star Wars: A New Hope* as there was "no underwear in space." Fisher says George Lucas told her, "What happens is you go to space and you become weightless...But then your body expands??? But your bra doesn't – so you get strangled by your own bra" (Fisher, *Wishful Drinking*, 2009, p. 89). Instead of wearing a bra, Fisher was forced to wear gaffer's tape, which is normally used to tape down cables to a stage. Gaffer's tape "is a heavy cotton cloth pressure sensitive tape with strong adhesive qualities" (Echo Tape, 2021). This situation seems like it would have provided measurable discomfort for Fisher.

After the events of *Star Wars: A New Hope*, Leia's position of power deteriorates as she becomes more love interest than leader. In *The Empire Strikes Back*, Leia is seen giving orders to pilots and soldiers on battle plans when the Rebel's Hoth base is under attack by the Empire. She is a leader in the Rebellion, but in this story, she becomes more reliant on Han Solo. Han is the one who comes to her rescue as the base starts to collapse, taking her to escape on the Millennium Falcon, but also away from her position of power.

She is also no longer the one standing up to Darth Vader in his attempts to destroy the Rebel Alliance and take control of the galaxy. It is now Luke Skywalker who deals exclusively with Darth Vader in *The Empire Strikes Back*. When in Vader's presence on Cloud City, Leia expresses her love to Han Solo as he is lowered into carbonite to become the frozen prize of Jabba the Hutt. It becomes clear that Luke is no longer

supposed to be seen as just a farm boy from Tatooine, but as a soon-to-be powerful Jedi. A children's pop-up book from 1980 detailing the events of *The Empire Strikes Back* confirms this because it focuses on Luke – Han and Leia are never mentioned. Leia is at least pictured on a couple of the final pages, though generally hidden behind flaps or off center. (Patricia Wynne (illustrator), 1980)

Rock Bottom

Star Wars draws inspiration from different cultural and mythological stories. One of the most prevalent is that of Arthurian Legend. Luke plays a young Arthur, the hero, while Leia “like the typical fairy-tale princess, is held captive” (Mackey-Kallis, 2001) by the Empire and later Jabba the Hutt. Through the progression of the trilogy, she becomes more like the damsel in distress and less of the leader she is. “Although Leia is portrayed as a fiery and feisty woman who clearly possesses a strong will, this persona is primarily developed to provide a ‘hard-to-get’ challenge for Han Solo. A classic ‘taming of the shrew’ dramatic motif, Leia’s indomitable spirit simply presents Han with a more interesting conquest as he teaches her to love and bend to his will” (Mackey-Kallis, 2001, pp. 202-227). She especially serves as a point of conflict between Han Solo and Luke Skywalker in *Episode V: The Empire Strikes Back* when she kisses Luke in front of Han to make him jealous. This makes Leia simply the love interest, and not only for Han Solo, but also for Luke Skywalker in Episodes IV and V as they do not yet know they are twins – creating in effect, a love triangle.

However, the portrayal of Princess Leia doesn't hit rock bottom until she was forced to be Jabba the Hutt's slave. Dressed in what Carrie Fisher described as “the bikini from hell. Like steel, not steel but hard plastic, and if you stood behind me you could see

straight to Florida” (Biggar, 2005, p. 143). This meant anyone standing behind her as she lay forcibly reclined on Jabba could see her private parts – especially since “there’s no underwear in space” (Buis, 2016). Before being forced into this revealing costume, Leia was disguised as a Bounty Hunter and covered from head to toe. She’s seen as dangerous while holding an active thermal detonator (the equivalent to a grenade). Leia loses this power once she’s put into her bikini costume. Now her purpose is to serve as a sexual pleasure to Jabba the Hutt and to the males in the audience. As John Berger says in *Ways of Seeing*, “To be naked is to be without disguise.” Leia is without her disguise. Now, she and Carrie Fisher are exposed to the male gaze of those around them, and to those who will continue to view her as a sexual object.

Despite her eventual escape from Jabba by strangling him with the chain linking her to her captor, the overly sexualized costume was dubbed “Slave Leia.” The issue with this is that the name focuses on the submissive part of Leia’s capture and not on her escape. As Slave Leia, she represents sexual temptation to a male audience who have been pining over her throughout the previous films, and not the powerful woman who strangles him with his own “patriarchal chains” (Berlatsky, 2015).

Today, *Star Wars* (backed by Disney values) seeks to retcon the Slave Leia interpretation to reinfuse her with the power that was taken away from her by calling her a slave. According to Merriam-Webster, “Retcon is a shortened form of retroactive continuity, and refers to a literary device in which the form or content of a previously established narrative is changed” (Merriam-Webster, 2021). In the fictional *Star Wars* book, *Bloodline*, Leia is renamed as a warrior by the leader of the Nikto cartel and Leia’s antagonist, Rinnrivin, who is awed by the fact that she killed Jabba the Hutt:

‘Huttslayer,’ Rinnrivin breathed in genuine reverence. ‘This is what we call you among ourselves, and it is a far greater title than either senator or princess could ever be. The Niktos know you for the warrior you are, Huttslayer, and you will always have friends among us.’ (Gray, *Bloodline*, 2017)

Though Rinnrivin is the antagonist to Leia, he serves as a messenger to the *Star Wars* fandom that when Leia killed Jabba, she was no longer his slave, but his slayer. Perhaps this message serves as a response to parents’ outrage at Slave Leia action figures being sold. The action figure was one of only two Princess Leia action figures in Hasbro’s entire Black series. (Jao, 2015) The Hasbro Black series is a collection of action figures packaged in sleek black packaging that sell at a higher price point compared to other action figures available. There were many other Leia outfits that could have been chosen that did not oversexualize Leia, and yet they chose to include – and name it – Slave Leia.

Star Wars and Women’s Rights

While *Star Wars* can retcon stories and attempt to make things right, some fans utilize Leia’s character for social agendas. Leia has become a sort of feminist icon – despite there being some discrepancies with this idea and her character arc. This feminist co-optation exists because fans create their own meaning for Leia’s character. For example, in Figure 3, Leia is seen on a poster with the caption, “A Woman’s Place is in the Resistance” making Leia akin to a revolutionary woman who is fighting for women’s rights. Leia wasn’t fighting for women’s rights but for the freedom of the galaxy being oppressed by the Empire.

Figure 3 A Woman's Place is in the Resistance (Corkins, 2017)

Perhaps the reason behind this has nothing to do with Princess Leia, but instead has to do with Carrie Fisher who was an advocate for women's rights. Mark Hamill, who played Luke Skywalker (Leia's brother) in *Star Wars* tweeted in response to the World-Wide Women's March in 2017 saying that Carrie Fisher would have stood with them had she been alive and how he considered it "an honor to see her standing with you today" (Hamill, 2017). The tweet is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Mark Hamill tweets about Carrie Fisher in relation to the World Wide Women's March in 2017. (Hamill, 2017)

Figure 5 A propaganda style poster from a Women's March in Los Angeles, California showing Princess Leia with the words "Resist" and "End Patriarchy" (Watercutter, 2017).

Figure 5 shows a propaganda style poster from a Women's March in Los Angeles, California with an image of Leia and the words, "Resist" and "End Patriarchy." Princess Leia was not fighting to end patriarchy. Sure, the evil regimes the Rebellion – and later the Resistance – were fighting against were run by males at the top, but the fight was not against patriarchy. They were fighting against totalitarian governments: first the Empire and then the First Order. Both of these emulated an "unflinching fascist image" (Hidalgo, 2016) and are representative of Hitler in World War II. The costumes of the Empire's Stormtroopers, Imperial officers, "and even Darth Vader's helmet resemble those worn by German Army members in World War II" (Klein, 2015). Indeed, the symbolic nature that the *Star Wars* story and its costumes represent are not meant to insight a patriarchal resistance, but a fight against something bigger and all-encompassing as World War II. Despite this, Leia and other female characters within *Star Wars* have had this idea of anti-patriarchy placed upon their characters by some of their fans to represent their cause as seen through these posters.

While there is nothing inherently wrong with utilizing a pop culture character in social movements, it is still interesting how the perception of the characters can change to fit the agenda. It is possible that Carrie Fisher and Princess Leia were merged into one person. Fisher was an outspoken feminist and proponent of gender equality, but she never tried to distance herself from Leia. As she said, “If it was a bad thing, I would have a bad life. It’s actually great. Those movies are great. I got to be the only girl in an all boy fantasy, and it’s a great role for women. She’s a very proactive character and gets the job done. So if you’re going to get typecast as something, that might as well be it for me” (Cooney, 2016). Fisher, like her feminist counterparts, looked for the good in Leia – chalking up the contradictions to an age-old Hollywood problem.

In some ways, post-Disney *Star Wars* capitalized on the feminist movement as an opportunity to sell to these consumers who were interpreting their characters as feminist icons. For instance, in 2018 (post-Disney *Star Wars*), a book titled *Women of the Galaxy* was published. The cover slip states the book written by Amy Ratcliffe with a foreword by Kathleen Kennedy and is illustrated by female and non-binary artists. The article detailing the release described the uniqueness of the book and how “there’s never really been a book like this before — one dedicated to the female characters of Star Wars across mediums” (Star Wars, 2018). The same could be said of how this book still doesn’t exist for the female characters’ male counterparts.

This post-Disney *Star Wars* book does a good job of telling each character’s story. Each character is given a blip that describes their part of the Star Wars story in a way that empowers women. For example, the book states how Leia’s “conviction overrides caution, so Leia decides to ask forgiveness rather than permission” (Ratcliffe,

2018, p. 114). The writing chooses to empower each female character and inspire their reader. Even the artwork in the book is done in a way that shows the women's power, and not their sexuality as the original movie poster showed Leia.

Fan Influence on Star Wars Art

Despite the work that Disney and *Star Wars* fans are putting into these characters, there are fan artists who continue to create sexualized fan art of the female *Star Wars* characters. One piece of fan art shows a sexualized depiction of Princess Leia and Mara Jade (a pre-Disney character - also known as an Extended Universe character) both with exaggerated breasts. The disproportionate additions are inaccurate representations of both of these characters.

Figure 6 Princess Leia and Mara Jade Fan art depicts these characters in an overtly sexual way. (Leia and Mara)

This returns to the idea that *Star Wars* was created to be a boy's fantasy; however, the post-Disney *Star Wars* now works to combat this portrayal of their female characters. At *Star Wars* Celebration – the convention for *Star Wars* fans – the franchise hosts an Art Show for the fandom's artists to showcase their work. The 2020 Art Show was hosted online and the artwork can be seen on *Star Wars*' website. To the observer, the artwork chosen from the online 2020 Art Show supports *Star Wars*'s message of inclusivity and equality. The female characters are created with a physical likeness to their live-action or

animated counterparts, and there are no exaggerations of body parts or lack of clothing to create a sexualized version of the characters. The art is simply a true representation of the character pictured. (Star Wars, 2020)

Ashley Eckstein: Voice of Ahsoka Tano, Business-owner, and Lifelong Star Wars Fan

Conventions like *Star Wars* Celebration actually served as a pivotal moment for gender equality in *Star Wars* fandom-wear and for *The Clone Wars* voice actress Ashley Eckstein. Fandom-wear is clothing that reflects a person's favorite franchise or fandom. For Eckstein, her fandom was *Star Wars*. Ashley Eckstein was cast as Ahsoka Tano in the animated series *Star Wars: The Clone Wars*. In 2008, as part of her new role, she began "travelling the nation going to *Star Wars* events and conventions" (Eckstein, 2018, p. 93). As an actress meeting with fans, she wanted to show off her love of *Star Wars* through her clothing, but she found there was a definite lack of *Star Wars* attire made for women. Eckstein, like her animated character, was determined to fix this inequality, so she went to Lucasfilm.

The first meeting she scheduled with the licensing team was cancelled, so Eckstein tried to reschedule it. Again, Lucasfilm cancelled, this time saying, "no to the meeting and no to [her] idea, because they only gave out licenses to reputable companies that could produce the merchandise for them" (Eckstein, 2018, p. 99). Eckstein was determined to fulfill the need she saw in the market, so she requested a third meeting. Lucasfilm had a representative call her to say she "should just settle for a men's size small, because women would not buy merchandise made for them" (Eckstein, 2018, p. 99).

However, despite Lucasfilm's rejection, Eckstein still believed there was a need in the market, so she researched sci-fi and fantasy conventions and "found that, on average, 45% of the attendees were women and girls. [She] also found out that 85 percent of consumer purchases at the time were being made by women" (Eckstein, 2018, p. 94). Armed with this research, she took what Lucasfilm had said and went on to launch her company: Her Universe. She hired people who knew things about licensing and running a business that she didn't know to help her succeed.

After setting up Her Universe and creating her pitch, she knew she was ready to meet with the licensing team at Lucasfilm. Eckstein happened to be visiting her friend Lynne Hale, who'd worked at Lucasfilm for over 30 years, when Howard Roffman, the head of Lucasfilm licensing walked by Hale's office. Hale chased him down and convinced him to listen to an impromptu pitch from Eckstein. Ashley Eckstein was finally given her chance to passionately explain how *Star Wars* is for everyone and how she had gone through all the steps that Lucasfilm required to become a licensing partner. Thanks to her friend, Lynne Hale, believing in her and helping her secure this opportunity, Her Universe was given "the rights to sell only on [their] website and at conventions. While this license felt incredibly restrictive, it was the best thing they could have done for [Her Universe]. It forced [them] to go directly to the fans to build Her Universe from the ground up" (Eckstein, 2018, p. 111). In this way, Eckstein was able to connect with fans and discover what they wanted in fandom-wear.

A few months after starting her company, a story came out about "a little girl named Katie who was bullied for carrying a *Star Wars* water bottle to school" because "*Star Wars* was for boys" (Eckstein, 2018, p. 130). Eckstein's business 'why' then

became not only about making female fandom-wear accessible, but to also create a safe space for fangirls to interact and talk about their love of *Star Wars* – without being bullied. This exemplifies one of the roadblocks Eckstein faced in convincing Lucasfilm to make *Star Wars* clothing for women and girls, and it is based in Gender Schema Theory. In 1981, psychologist Sandra Bem introduced a theory that “asserted that children learn about male and female roles from the culture in which they live. According to the theory, children adjust their behavior to align with the gender norms of their culture from the earliest stages of social development” (Cherry, 2020). The story about Katie shows how the children who were bullying her for liking *Star Wars* had been indoctrinated by their upbringing and societal cues to believe that *Star Wars* was a male-gendered franchise. The Lucasfilm representatives also seemed to believe the same thing, showing they too had the same notion as the children.

Eckstein started Her Universe in 2010 in what was still the pre-Disney *Star Wars* era and serves as a great reminder of the work still needed to break the stigma that *Star Wars* was only for boys. Despite how far *Star Wars* had come at this point – after all, *The Clone Wars*’ Ahsoka was groundbreaking as a powerful female Jedi – there was still work to be done to create a more inclusive merchandising environment. Ultimately, it took Eckstein to help them realize the value of creating merchandise for women. (Her Universe, n.d.)

Retconning the Prequel Trilogy

The Clone Wars series itself served in some ways as a retcon of the prequel trilogy. Eckstein’s Ahsoka Tano would be the first female Jedi lead, even before Disney’s Rey. The series would also help in repairing some of the damage done to Padmé

Amidala's character during the prequel movies by showcasing her strength through episodes centered around her like "Corruption" (Season 3 Episode 5). In this episode, Padmé visits the Duchess Satine of Mandalore (a planet not aligned with the Republic during the Clone Wars and who can't get easy access to supplies) to help "Satine and her people get access to the resources they need. Soon after her arrival, it becomes clear that the planet's isolation has allowed corruption to take root" (Ivey, 2020). The beauty of this episode is that not only is Padmé shown as a strong, independent woman, but she works with another woman of similar strengths. This Clone Wars Padmé reflects the powerful and beloved Queen first seen in Episode I of the Prequels. Unfortunately, Padmé Amidala experiences a gradual decline in her power throughout the three prequel movies. This decline is exemplified by the costumes worn by Natalie Portman, the actress behind Padmé Amidala.

Padme and the Prequels

In *Star Wars: The Phantom Menace*, the 14-year-old Queen Amidala's planet is being blockaded by the Trade Federation. The corrupt Trade Federation wants her to sign a treaty allowing unfair trade between her planet and them. The Trade Federation attempts to capture her to make her sign a treaty, but Queen Amidala stands firm: she will not sign any treaty. Later, after narrowly escaping capture, Queen Amidala begs the Galactic Senate for aid against the Trade Federation; however, they refuse to aid in her plight. She returns to her planet and begs the Gungans, who are the underwater inhabitants of Naboo for help. Queen Amidala fights alongside her people to take back control of the capital while the Gungans fight the enemy's droid army. Throughout all this, her costumes as Queen Amidala are meant "to reflect the confines and constraints of

protocol and ceremonial customs in highly detailed costumes” (Biggar, 2005, p. 43).

Queen Amidala is portrayed as strong, independent, and capable of wielding power for good.

Episode II tells a very different story as Queen Amidala is now Senator Padmé Amidala working in the Galactic Senate. There are multiple assassination attempts on her life leading to her receiving a Jedi escort, Anakin Skywalker, and thus beginning her departure from powerful leader to the love interest. “As the story of their love unfolds, her wardrobe highlights the mood of romance and passion at the idyllic Naboo Lake Country retreat. Unlike her regal and chaste attire as Naboo’s sovereign, we were able to show a sultry sexiness in more revealing costumes” according to costume designer, Trisha Biggar. (Dressing a Galaxy, 2005, p. 96).

Padmé, while still in her Senatorial gown, puts Anakin in his place when she catches him staring at her. In this scene, she remains the dignified Senator, wearing an unrevealing black dress. However, when she and Anakin arrive on Naboo, she is dressed in a backless, flowing white ombre dress. The confines of her senatorial position’s wardrobe no longer exist, and she is free to fully become Anakin’s love interest. Figure 7 shows Padmé and Anakin moments before they kiss and she tells him, “No, I shouldn’t have done that” in reference to the kiss they should not have shared.

Figure 7 Padme looks at Anakin on Naboo. (Anika)

John Berger references a look that women give who were either modeling for a photo or a work of art. The gaze is always the same showing that she is aware that her body is being seen, and she is “responding with calculated charm to the man whom she knows is looking at her” (Berger). This gaze John Berger makes note of is repeated several times by Padmé when she is in the presence of Anakin, including in the above image. She knows he sees her, but the confines of duty still linger. An example of the gaze from *Ways of Seeing* is shown in Figure 8 to compare:

Figure 8 An example John Berger gives of a woman and the gaze showing that she is aware that her body is being seen. (Berger)

Later on in *Episode II*, Padmé and Anakin are inside in a room lit only by the fire in the fireplace. Here, they begin to discuss their feelings for each other; Anakin wants Padmé despite the consequences, but Padmé is still driven by her sense of duty to the Republic, and the scandal that would follow should a Jedi and Senator elope. Her words say she cannot commit to a life in secret with Anakin, but her dress tells a different story. In taking away her agency by putting her in this dress, Padmé's words no longer matter.

Designed by George Lucas himself, it was a very revealing skintight black dress with a corset that Natalie Portman said made it difficult to wear as it was so tight (Star Wars, 2002). It makes her appear more as a sex symbol; whereas before, her costumes

were light and airy with an innocence about them. She is again subjected to Anakin's male gaze, and her look in Figure 9 is similar to the look John Berger describes:

Figure 9 Padme Looks at Anakin (Lancemannon, n.d.)

Later in the episode, Padmé and Anakin are caught trying to rescue Obi-Wan Kenobi and are then scheduled for a public execution by beasts. As Padmé and Anakin are being moved to their execution poles, Padmé admits her love to Anakin. During this scene, Padmé is dressed in a white skin tight ensemble that accentuates her feminine figure. Padmé slips something into her mouth as she is led to her execution pillar. The trio, chained to pillars, watch as the beasts are released into the arena. Padmé immediately begins to pick the lock on her cuffs using what she had slipped into her mouth and climbs to the top of the pillar. While she is doing this – away from Anakin – her love interest worries about her, oblivious to the fact that she has already climbed on top of her pillar, securing the high ground. Once the beasts are released, Padmé's beast called the nexu climbs up her pillar and slashes her back, ripping her ensemble. She gains back some of her power when she kicks the nexu, stunning it. The tear turns Padmé's ensemble into a midriff exposing her stomach, further portraying Padmé as a damsel in

distress for Anakin to come and rescue which he does by killing the nexu with the beast that he tamed with the Force.

However, despite this occurrence, Padmé is quite capable of taking care of herself. She is more independent when she is separated from Anakin. Once the Jedi and their newly discovered Clone army evacuates them from the arena, the ship carrying Padmé, Anakin, and Obi-Wan takes a hit from enemy fire sending Padmé and a Clone Trooper to the ground. Anakin is distraught that Padmé could be in danger; whereas, she recovers from her fall and begins ordering the Clone Trooper to assemble more troops to get to the hanger where Anakin and Obi-Wan are fighting Count Dooku. This scene exemplifies the fact that Padmé is a strong leader and not just a damsel in distress or just a love interest.

By the end of *Episode II*, Padmé and Anakin are secretly married. The sense of duty to her role of Senator and his role of Jedi still exists, but their love has overpowered the original urge to silence their feelings and continue carrying out their respective roles without each other. With Anakin, Padmé is no longer just a Senator, but his wife and the bearer of the next generation.

In *Episode III: Revenge of the Sith*, the audience discovers alongside Anakin that Padmé is pregnant. Her role in the film quickly becomes that of wife and soon-to-be mother and no longer the strong, independent woman she was in the first episodes. This episode could have shown Padmé as more than just an expectant mother who must stay in the background. In a *Revenge of the Sith* deleted scene, Padmé is seen in a meeting with a group of other Senators discussing the founding of the Rebellion – the same group that Padmé's daughter, Leia would someday end up leading. Instead, it was decided that the

focus should be on Anakin as the majority of the movie focuses on his fall to the dark side. While this is disappointing from the point of view that Padmé could have been so much more than how she appeared in the final cut, it should not be surprising. Padmé is not the main character and this is not her story. She is meant as a story propellant for Anakin, an antithesis to Anakin's fall to the Dark Side, as well as the biological reason for Luke and Leia – the stars of the first trilogy.

Figure 10 Concept art depicting Padme holding a baby. (Biggar, 2005, p. 167)

Her connection with Anakin is also why she dies at the end of *Episode III*.

Original concept art shows her being depicted as a mother holding a baby that one can only assume is Luke or Leia. In actuality, she dies in childbirth as Anakin foresees in a nightmare, further adding to the fact that this is about Anakin and his fall to the Dark Side – not Padmé. She had to die in order for his fall to be complete. She was the light to his dark, but also the catalyst to behavior that took him outside of the Jedi Order's rules and regulations meant to keep Jedi from falling to the Dark Side. After Luke and Leia were

born, she had served her purpose; the original trilogy was set up with the two Skywalker children who would fight against the evils of the Empire – and their father.

This interpretation of Padmé, while understandable in the sense of the original storyline's purpose, does not continually show Padmé's strong character. The animated movie and series, *The Clone Wars* was a step in the right direction during pre-Disney times, but it wasn't until after Disney bought *Star Wars* that real change in the perception of Padmé's character and other overlooked female characters began.

E.K. Johnston wrote a trilogy of books, published starting in 2019, about Padmé Amidala's life. The first book titled *Queen's Shadow*, follows Amidala as she adjusts to life as a Senator, but it also reintroduces a character originally played by Keira Knightly in *The Phantom Menace*, Sabé, who is Padmé Amidala's decoy as well as one of her handmaidens. Sabé, the doppelganger of Amidala, often pretends to be her in order to protect Amidala. She is a true representation of loyalty as she never turns down a mission – no matter how dangerous it might be. (Johnston, *Queen's Shadow*, 2019)

Queen's Shadow develops the relationship between Sabé and Padmé, but also serves to add depth to Padmé's character and show her struggles and successes in becoming a senator in the Galactic Senate. It is “truly a celebration of women and the relationships they have with each other, as well as championing collaboration and working together for a better whole” (Dempster, 2019). In *Attack of the Clones* and *Revenge of the Sith*, Padmé is rarely shown in her full senatorial mode – instead being shown as the love interest. This book rectifies this and shows the strength and compassion Padmé has that makes her a good senator.

The second book, *Queen's Peril*, is a prequel which focusses on Amidala's time as Queen of Naboo with its ending coinciding with *The Phantom Menace*. It also explains in more depth the importance of the Queen's handmaidens. The Queen's handmaidens are girls picked by the head of security to serve and protect the Queen. On the surface they appear to be an extension of the Queen's appearance and power; however, they can serve as bodyguards, gather information through deception, or help advise the Queen. (Johnston, *Queen's Peril*, 2020)

This book not only serves to deepen the relationship between the handmaidens and Padmé Amidala, but also to show that the handmaidens are more than just a beautifully outfitted band of girls. In the book, the youngest of Queen Amidala's handmaidens, Saché, is caught delivering messages for the group resisting the Trade Federation's invasion. Her loyalty to her Queen and the Royal Naboo Security Forces is tested as she is tortured, but the twelve-year-old Saché never gave the Trade Federation what they wanted. She was "covered with cauterized lacerations, bright red lines on her hands and face and, one assumed on her body beneath the nearly ruined orange robe" (Johnston, *Queen's Peril*, 2020, p. 245). Saché's bravery and ability to survive without breaking as a result of the Trade Federation's torture device is just one example of the feminine power packed into the handmaidens, a group of 'background' characters, in *The Phantom Menace*.

The final installment, *Queen's Hope*, shows Padmé married to Anakin and the struggles they face because of the secret they chose to share (their love and marriage). The marriage doesn't stop Padmé from doing her duty, and she finds herself on an undercover mission. She requests Sabé pretend to be her once again to maintain the

impression that she is still in the Senate. Anakin, off fighting in the Clone Wars is rarely in the book, serving mostly as confirmation to Sabé that the reason for the changes in Padmé's life are because of him.

In a way, I don't think this final installment is about Padmé. By all means, Padmé has a stellar storyline where she is the one in charge and calling the shots, but I think this is Sabé's story. Sabé, always the one to come back to serve Padmé when called, has finally discovered a life she feels worthy of leading: freeing slaves on Tatooine. She tells Padmé she's done being her decoy, to not ask her to do it again, and Padmé concedes. Sabé, always in the shadow of Padmé, is finally allowed to be her own self.

Sexuality

While these books retconned the likes of both Padmé and Sabé, they were also some of the first *Star Wars* books to handle gender fluidity and homosexuality through its supporting characters. E.K. Johnston's previous release, *Star Wars: Ahsoka*, hints at the possibility of homosexuality, but it's portrayed as one sided and never specifically spelled out. This changes with the release of *Queen's Peril* and *Queen's Hope*.

In *Queen's Peril*, it is established that two of Padmé's handmaidens are in love with each other: Saché and Yané. Then in *Queen's Hope*, the reader discovers that they have been married and have started a family. Saché is a member of Naboo's legislature and as such needed an aide to assist her in the day-to-day activities of an elected official. Saché ends up hiring an aid named Tepoh who tells her, "Sometimes I wake up and I want to be perceived as some degree female, but sometimes I don't" (Johnston, *Queen's Hope*, 2021). Tepoh is referred to using the pronouns zhe/zher throughout the book which

are gender neutral pronouns “for people who feel closer to their feminine side but are quite clearly non-binary” (Queer, n.d.).

The Sequel Trilogy

While Disney certainly played into the LGBTQ movement through its book releases, the newest *Star Wars* trilogy (Episodes 7 to 9) utilizes the popularity of the feminist movements to create the first live-action *Star Wars* to portray a female lead character. Looking at *The Force Awakens*' original movie poster, it is clear that the story will be about Rey, the young female scavenger. She is featured on the movie poster as the central figure as shown below.

Figure 11 *Star Wars: The Force Awakens* Movie Poster (Disney, n.d.)

Despite this apparent female centrality, one can't help but notice the similarities between *The Force Awakens* and the original *Star Wars* (later renamed *A New Hope*) wherein Rey becomes Luke. The likeness starts with the desert worlds in which they live

on – Rey lives on Jakku and Luke on Tatooine. The planet name is one of the only differentiators between the empty, harsh worlds they live on. “Both have to scrape by on a paltry living—Luke through his work on his uncle’s moisture farm, Rey through scavenging and trading in her salvaged materials to the junkyard owner Unkar Plutt. Luke and Rey’s respective journeys into heroic adventure begin soon after they come into possession of an astromech droid concealing important plans” (McDowell, 2019). The similarity between the storylines takes away from *The Force Awakens*’ female lead since the story has already been done. It is a female reiteration of the original *Star Wars*, and with that, Rey’s character is not as groundbreaking as it could have been. If the story reflected the feminist interests that seemed to influence the choice of Rey as the lead, the character would have been as groundbreaking as Ahsoka Tano in *The Clone Wars*.

While I don’t think Rey was an original or innovative character, her merchandise was in high demand; yet, somehow “Disney failed to include Rey in their merchandising line upon the 2015 release of *Episode VII: The Force Awakens*. Consumers quickly began to protest on social media with the #Where’s Rey movement demanding Rey products” (Morgan, 2020). It’s surprising that Disney missed out on an opportunity to capitalize on their lead character – regardless their gender. Furthermore, Disney somehow didn’t think to utilize gender-based marketing for this film. If they had, there wouldn’t have been a fan campaign for Rey merchandise with the hashtag “Where’s Rey.” This example echoes Ashley Eckstein’s experience with Lucasfilm and how they believed women wouldn’t buy fandom clothing made for them, showing that even with all that Disney had been doing to balance the fan-base, the parent company still missed the same mark its acquisition had missed years earlier.

In 2017, Forces of Destiny dolls came out along with a new series of animated shorts with the same name – perhaps in response to the outrage over the lack of Rey toys. The Forces of Destiny series stars the female heroes of Star Wars. These dolls are a cross between action figures and Barbie dolls. They are the same size as a Barbie doll, but have the realistic characteristics of action figures. Some may view this as a feminist step in the right direction; however, I think of it as *Femvertising*. ‘Femvertising’ or feminist advertising “is the use of feminist ideals by brands to sell their products” (Gupta, 2017). All the characters are shown wearing the clothing that makes them successful, and they are not overly sexualized. The coloring used in the packaging suggests these products are marketed towards girls with the *Star Wars* logo being purple and orange instead of its normal yellow color. These dolls came out before the release of the second sequel trilogy movie: *The Last Jedi*, which is why Rey is shown below in two different costumes – one for each movie. Disney was not was not going to make the same mistake again.

Figure 12 Forces of Destiny Dolls depict several female characters from the Star Wars universe. (BrocksTravels, 2017)

The Last Jedi does a great job of including women in this movie; however, the mere act of inclusion does not make a film great – especially when there is a lack of character development, story cohesiveness, and a strain on the suspension of disbelief.

These are each shown through three of the supporting female characters: Amilyn Holdo, Rose Tico, and General Leia Organa.

Vice Admiral Amilyn Holdo sacrifices herself for the rest of the Rebel fleet by jumping to hyperspace through the bad First Order's main ship, tearing it apart. The problem with this grand gesture is there is no sense of attachment to her character. For a *Star Wars* fan who only watches the movies, this is the first time they would have ever heard of her. There is no real character development because there is no baseline for her character. Even I, a huge *Star Wars* fan, was unimpressed by her sacrifice when I first watched the movie because it was as if an extra was the one to save the day and not a main or well-known character such as Rey or Leia.

However, it turns out she was introduced to the *Star Wars* universe before this movie came out in the Young Adult book titled *Leia: Princess of Alderaan* which centers around the 16-year-old title character. Leia becomes friends with the young Amilyn Holdo. In the book, Holdo eventually helps Leia evade Imperial detainment by lying to the Imperial officer about their previous location where they had just saved the Rebel fleet from being destroyed by the evil Empire. (Gray, *Leia: Princess of Alderaan*, 2017) Where Disney fails to provide any character development with *The Last Jedi*, their book develops Holdo's character from a carefree girl to selfless supporter of the Rebellion working to take down the Empire with Leia. It's only with this background that Holdo's sacrifice makes sense, and considering the book's target audience was 'young adults' it's no wonder the film's audience and I found this scene unimpressive.

Rose Tico fails to match the tone of *Star Wars* and ruins Finn's sacrificial lamb moment. While attempting to save the Resistance by flying his ship into the weapon that

is in the process of destroying the rebel stronghold, Finn, the black former First Order trooper, is knocked out of his collision path by Rose. This destroys Finn's moment. He was about to redeem himself for being part of the evil First Order by sacrificing his life for the common good. Rose's "choice would have gotten everyone killed, if not for Luke's serendipitous arrival" (Weiland, n.d.). Then Rose further undermines Finn's action by saying, "That's how we're going to win. Not by fighting what we hate, but saving what we love!" One of the only other characters to embody this sentiment in the *Star Wars* universe is the pacifist Duchess Satine from the *Clone Wars* series. She gets away with it because she is introduced as a pacifist and therefore her behavior is justified. Rose's realization comes as an unwelcome surprise to the audience because they are in the middle of a battle of good versus evil, where pacifism isn't an option.

Finally, the scene named by fans as "Space Leia" shatters the audience's suspension of disbelief. Suspension of disbelief is "defined as a willingness to suspend one's critical faculties and believe something is surreal" (Kadish, 2018). After a heart wrenching force bond between Kylo Ren and his mother, General Leia Organa, we see Kylo Ren decide not to destroy the bridge of her ship. Then some of Ren's subordinates destroy the bridge anyway. The moment seems to communicate that Leia will die knowing there is good in her son (a common theme in *Star Wars*). The audience is of course upset that Leia is being blown up, but they also know that Carrie Fisher passed away in 2016 before the release of *The Last Jedi*, so it would be logical that she dies in this scene being that she's physically unable to appear in the final installment. Instead, Leia reaches out with the Force and flies herself back to the ship and lives. The scene comes across as an overpowered character defying the odds of survival in space through

the use of a Force power that the audience has never seen. It is so different that it strains the suspension of disbelief and makes it indeed look like this action is impossible.

The Rise of Skywalker ends with Ben Solo, the redeemed Kylo Ren, coming to Rey's aid to defeat the evil Emperor Palpatine where it is apparent that their Force dyad established in *The Last Jedi* is still in effect. A Force dyad "is when two beings coexist at the same time in the galaxy and share a level of Force capability that compliments the other. Instead of a singular user being one with the Force, the dyad is one being together and then coupled with the Force" (Dunkin, 2022). This connection allows Rey to pass Luke's blue lightsaber to Ben without being next to him. This dyad also enables the evil Emperor Palpatine to take the power from their dyad to restore himself.

In a poetic ending, Rey fights against her grandfather, Emperor Palpatine who claims to be "all the Sith" to which Rey replies that she is "all the Jedi." The light of the Jedi wins out against Palpatine's evil, but in the process of killing Palpatine, Rey dies. Ben, who was injured when Palpatine knocked him off a cliff, climbs up and saves Rey through the Force. She comes back to life and they kiss. For a moment, they are both happy. Then suddenly Ben dies, but he dies a Jedi's death in that his corpse vanishes similarly to his namesake, Jedi Master Obi-Wan Kenobi. At the same moment, his mother General Leia Organa vanishes in the same way leaving audiences to believe that Ben didn't die when he was thrown off that cliff because his mother was with him, keeping him alive through the Force. In effect, Ben uses the last of his (and his mother's) Life Force to save Rey who was willing to sacrifice herself for the greater good of the galaxy as a true Jedi would.

At the end of the film, Rey returns to Tatooine, the planet where *Star Wars* began, where Luke was raised by an uncle and aunt not related to him by blood but who loved him all the same. When an old woman asks who she is, Rey responds, “I’m Rey,” and then as she looks at Luke and Leia’s Force ghosts, the children of Anakin Skywalker and adds, “Rey Skywalker.” The point of the title, *Rise of Skywalker*, and the significance of Rey taking the Skywalker last name reiterates the theme that blood doesn’t necessarily make you family. Luke experienced that as did his sister Leia who was raised by her adoptive parents Bail and Breha Organa who loved her like their own. Rey recognized her grandfather as evil and incapable of love, but by then she had already been taken in by a new family: Luke and Leia Skywalker. This arc helps to redeem the unoriginality of *The Force Awakens* by showing Rey as a Jedi who would die for the greater good of the galaxy as Luke and Leia had risked their lives fighting against the same evils.

Conclusion

Star Wars has certainly come a long way since its beginning in the late 1970s, and as such, this paper barely scratches the surface of all the *Star Wars* shows, movies, books, and comics in existence today. Throughout this paper, I have focused primarily on the Skywalker saga that encompasses nine movies, an animated movie and series, as well as books. Throughout the saga, the women of *Star Wars* on and off the screen have faced challenges on the basis of their sex. These women, despite the mistreatment and sexualization of their characters, became feminist icons to fans. It is clear that Disney recognizes the importance of women playing equitable roles in *Star Wars*, but they still falter and fall prey to diversity casting and subpar character development; though they are learning and growing in this through the creation of new medias.

The *Star Wars* story is far from over. With new shows airing every year on Disney+ for the foreseeable future, *Star Wars* has the opportunity to delve deeper into their existing character's stories and create new ones that improve on the injustices done to previous characters. Already, *Andor* expands on Mon Mothma, a leader of the Rebellion. It shows her in a new light as one of the founding members of the Rebellion, working publicly as an 'irritation' but secretly to amass resources to overthrow the evil Empire. The audience has only ever seen a glancing image of Mon Mothma's leadership skills in *Return of the Jedi*, *Rogue One*, *Star Wars Rebels*, and *The Clone Wars* animated series. Although she is a supporting character in these, her actual role in the *Star Wars* universe is much greater.

Star Wars serves as a reflection of the society it was created in, and it will continue to change and grow as times change. Hopefully, as time goes on, fans and creators alike will continually realize the importance of strong, well-rounded characters that can delve deeper into new stories. As Shmi Skywalker tells her son in *The Phantom Menace*, "You can't stop change any more than you can stop the suns from setting." In other words, change is inevitable, and the pattern of *Star Wars* shows that change is occurring in the right direction, but a word of warning to the future creators: Diversity for the sake of diversity doesn't rewrite a poorly told story.

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